

TEACHING LEARNING FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

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Abstract: In our country, since the first days of independence, tourist services in the service sector have been treated as a priority area of economic development, attention to which has increased to the level of state policy. The necessary organizational and legal mechanisms for the development of the industry have been created, relevant government regulations have been adopted, and work in this direction continues now

Key words: tourism, hospitality industry, communication skills, tourism market.

1 INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the world's fastest growing industries and is a major source of income for many countries. Being a people-oriented industry, tourism also provides many jobs which have helped revitalize local economies. However, like other forms of development, tourism can also cause its share of problems, such as social dislocation, loss of cultural heritage, economic dependence and ecological degradation. Tourism plays an important role worldwide and is a steadily growing economic sector. Customer satisfaction and the creation of a strong brand therefore play an ever larger part for each company. In the competitive and constantly changing tourism industry, it is a challenge to develop customer contact optimally and continuously. Teaching and Learning for a Sustainable Future is rooted in a new vision of education, a vision that helps students better understand the world in which they live, addressing the complexity and interconnectedness of problems such as poverty, wasteful consumption, environmental degradation, urban decay, population growth, health, conflict the violation of human rights that threaten our future.

2 METHODOLOGY

The program assists teachers to empower young people to face such local and global problems with hope and confidence. This vision of education requires a holistic, interdisciplinary approach. It also requires us to reorient education systems, policies and practices in order to empower everyone, young and old, to make decisions and act in culturally appropriate and locally relevant ways to redress the problems that threaten our common future. Teaching and Learning for a Sustainable Future enable teachers to plan learning experiences that empower their students to develop and evaluate alternative revisions of a sustainable future and to work creatively with others to help bring their visions into effect. There are over 60 million teachers in the world – and each one is a key agent for bringing about the changes in lifestyles and systems we need. For this reason, innovative teacher education is an important part of educating for a sustainable future. The multimedia

format of Teaching and Learning for a Sustainable Future means that it can be accessed and used in a great many ways by teachers, student teachers, teacher educators, curriculum developers, education policy makers and authors of educational materials. Education is critical for promoting sustainable development and improving the capacity of the people to address environment and development issues.

Communication skills are an important element of hospitality industry. Understanding of performance expectations are keys to the achievement of tourist satisfaction. Communication is vital to the success of tourism businesses since it is only through the effective use of communication that tourism marketers can offer to customers tangible cues about those intangible experiences. Also, while communication is an essential component in the conduct of any service business, it has got an overarching role in tourism. Tourists are individuals who want to escape from the routines of the mundane world. They want to experience 'the other' aspect of their selves not allowed to be expressed in the ordinary life settings. Such a conceptualization of the tourism phenomenon gives us clues about the type of communication that will be appreciated by tourist.

Good oral and written communication skills are the top skills important to hospitality practitioners at different position levels. Good English communication during the study will add value to students' education. According to that fact the hospitality program itself will encourage critical thinking and for example tourism problem solving when it is necessary. In the tourism industry supply and demand side must communicate perfectly in order to ensure quality and needed performance standards. In the business tourism practice oral communication is a bit higher than written communication, but both categories are rated high.

Tourism in Uzbekistan is getting one of the most efficient sectors of the economy. The market participants focus their efforts on the development of professional management, modern marketing and development of infrastructure. The government actively

promotes this process, at both national and regional level.

It is widely known that for the effective operation of the sector it should be provided with highly qualified specialists. If talking about the trends of development of national education in tourism, it is good to note that while improving the quality of service the sector companies started placing much emphasis on upgrading professional qualifications of their employees. Basic skills in tourism and management turn ever important as well.

3 DISCUSSION

The generation of specialists are trained in Uzbekistan demonstrates both higher level of professional training and aspiration for further advancing of their skills and knowledge in this field. Further improvement of the tourism industry will not only attract investment in the national economy, but also the active integration of Uzbekistan into the international community and its promotion in the world market and development of national economy. Providing tourists with better cultural-informative materials, active public campaign on attracting tourists to the country, active participation of Uzbekistan in international tourism fairs are the main goals of our common work.

Uzbekistan has a huge potential, favorable geopolitical position, rich cultural heritage. For the years of independence, development of tourism infrastructure has been activated, as well as attractive tourist image worked out and the system of education in this area formed.

Up-to-date problem of our national tourism industry is further development and improvement of training of highly skilled specialists at the level of international educational standards, creation of conditions for the implementation and effective use of the potential of youngsters, especially those from regions of the country, as well as expansion of international cooperation in higher education sphere.

Since communication with different stakeholders and for different purposes demand different skills, it is important for students to have mastery over a comprehensive set of commonly used media and formats. Teachers of tourism should demonstrate how communication skills such as conveying information clearly in speech and writing, and listening carefully, contribute to the successful operation of a tourism business. Communication skills gained outside of the classroom are significant. Also, many students gain a great deal of industry relevant communication skills during their internship, part-time jobs, or as volunteers for industrial events. Participation in extracurricular activities such as speaking, writing and poster designing competitions can also boost and fine-tune the communication skills of tourism students. Nevertheless, despite all these inputs, many human resource managers complain that a larger number of fresh recruits considerably lack in critical communication skills.

CONCLUSIONS

Modern development of the tourism industry acknowledges the need of modernization of the training system for the taking into account the existing realities and prospects. As a result of retraining and professional participants of the tourism market, the development of industrial science, the integration of vocational education in the practical activities of the organizations the national tourism industry shows stable growth dynamics for several years.

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